

MATHEMATICAL MODELLING OF MASS TRANSFER AND FOULING PROCESSES IN PRESSURELESS FILTERS: A 2D MODEL FOR CYLINDRICAL POROUS MEDIA

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Abstract. The mathematical model allows for the evaluation of the performance efficiency of the water filter, taking into account changes in concentration, porosity, pressure values and the fouling process. To select the appropriate problem-solving strategy, scientific research conducted over the past 10–15 years on the mathematical modelling of this process was analysed. A mathematical model and a numerical algorithm describing a system of partial differential equations and their corresponding initial and boundary conditions have been developed to solve the problem. Using the proposed mathematical model and taking into account a number of factors, it is possible to predict the concentration variation in a cylindrical porous medium over the required time interval.

Keywords. Brinkman-Darcy equations, hydrodynamics of porous media, mass transport, numerical approximation, liquid purification

Introduction. According to the law of conservation of mass, within a closed volume mass neither disappears nor is created; it is only observed to move from one place to another. The difference between the mass entering and leaving the medium is equal to the volume of mass accumulated in the medium, and this equilibrium is always maintained. If the volume of liquid entering the medium is greater than the volume of liquid leaving it, this indicates a mass accumulation in the medium, which increases the pressure and reduces porosity. A decrease in porosity, in turn, affects the flow. In a porous medium, fluid flow is driven by pressure gradients and the force of gravity. The flow rate is directly proportional to the medium's permeability and inversely proportional to its viscosity. Changes in the concentration of particles in the fluid occur as a result of advection (transport by flow), diffusion (spread due to concentration gradients) and fouling (deposition).

For cylindrical porous filters, the flow is typically expressed by the Darcy or Brinkman–Darcy equations. The mass conservation equation for the liquid particles describes the movement, dispersion and loss of particles within the filter. The main

processes are advection, diffusion and fouling; advection describes the movement of particles together with the fluid, and the greater the flow rate, the more pronounced the transport. The process of diffusion describes the microscopic dispersion of particles as they move from an area of high concentration to one of low concentration. For solutions, the advection–diffusion–reaction system is employed, while for adsorption Langmuir or similar kinetic models are used. Fouling denotes the reduction in concentration resulting from particles adhering to the porous walls. During the filtration process, particles adhere to the pore walls and accumulate on the filter surface, resulting in a reduction in porosity and the build-up of substances on the filter surface. The fouling process is characterised by the accumulation of solid particles in the porous medium or on filter surfaces, resulting in reduced porosity, increased hydraulic resistance and decreased filter efficiency. In a porous medium, fouling kinetics occur as a result of two opposing processes. The first is the attachment of particles to the filter surface as they are carried by the flow, This process is concentration-dependent: the higher the concentration, the faster the

particles accumulate, and the probability of particles adhering to the porous surface depends on particle diameter, fluid chemistry and the complexity of the medium. The second process is erosion, which depends on the concentration of sediment; the greater the concentration, the higher the likelihood of washout. Both processes depend on the flow rate: the lower the flow rate, the greater the concentration build-up; the faster the flow, the higher the likelihood of erosion. The adhesion of particles to the pore walls and the accumulation of sedimentary rocks lead to changes in porosity. As porosity decreases, permeability drops sharply because the available voids for fluid flow become narrower. Time-dependent changes in porosity: the reduction in porosity and permeability due to particle settling are given by a specialised colmatation equation. The dependence of permeability on porosity is determined based on the Kozeny–Karman relationship, which is expressed in a normalized form relative to the initial state. In many cases, the finite difference method, conservative schemes and Samarsky methods are employed, and stability conditions (CFL, etc.) are presented. Using the model, filter efficiency, service life, pressure distribution and fouling dynamics are predicted in advance. The coupled heat–mass–moisture transfer in catalytic porous media and soil masses is also studied with such models. By means of finite-difference and steady-state numerical schemes, these systems can be solved to enable the pre-assessment of mass exchange and colmatation, and the optimisation of design and operation for pressureless or low-pressure filters.

The model presented for the filtration of liquid solutions in a cylindrical porous filter is based on the Brinkman–Darcy equations and describes the fluid movement in the porous medium; where porosity and permeability are linked by the Kozeny–Karman relationship. The transport of dissolved substances is represented by an advection–diffusion–reaction system, and the adsorption process is accounted for using LDF kinetics and the Langmuir isotherm. The model also includes the colmatation equation, which describes the settling of particles and the reduction of the filter's porosity over time. An algorithm based on

the finite difference method has been developed for the numerical solution, in which the pressure is adjusted iteratively using the conjugate gradient method, and stability is ensured by the Courant–Friedrichs–Lewy condition. The proposed approach ensures the interrelated analysis of hydrodynamics, mass transfer and adsorption processes [1, 11].

In the integrated mathematical model of the radial filtration process in a cylindrical filter, the flow is directed from the outer layer into the inner cavity. The free-stream regions are described by the Navier–Stokes equations, considering the motion of an incompressible fluid. Filtration through the porous layer is expressed on the basis of Darcy's law, and the pressure distribution is determined by Poisson's equation. The transport of dissolved substances is modelled using the advection–diffusion equation. The model also incorporates a mechanism for the evolution of porosity over time (i.e. densification or clogging), allowing the interrelated dynamics of the pressure–velocity–porosity–concentration parameters to be observed. Analyses have shown that taking into account the vertical orientation of the cylindrical filter has a significant effect on reducing energy consumption and increasing process selectivity [2, 11].

[3] mathematical model of the mass transfer process in a complex porous medium in the form of a hollow cylinder with the specified height has been developed. The influence of the porous medium parameters on the pressure distribution process has been investigated.

In this article, the problem of diffusion- and convection-based filtration of a substance through the pores of a porous medium is investigated. As an example, a circular cylinder through which the filtration process takes place in the direction of the axis is considered. The cylinder is filled with a sorbent, that is, an absorbent material through which contaminated water or liquid solutions are passed. Within the framework of the problem, a system of two partial differential equations (PDEs) is derived. This approach makes it possible to reduce the 2D axisymmetric mass exchange problem from a system

of PDEs to an initial-value problem for a system of first-order ordinary differential equations (ODEs) [4, 7].

In this study, a Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) model is presented for modelling the microfiltration process using hollow fibre membranes to separate 2D materials from their dispersion. Microfiltration has been proposed as an economically efficient method for producing 2D materials, using a dispersion containing the solute (graphene), the contaminant (un-exfoliated graphite) and the solvent. The model investigated the effect of the pressure difference across a contaminant material (graphite) with a planar structure on the transmembrane pressure (TMP) and the filtration of the solute. The calculations were carried out using COMSOL Multiphysics, where the Navier–Stokes equations and the mass conservation equations were solved jointly, and flow and mass exchange were modelled in a two-dimensional domain [5].

The flow and mass-transfer characteristics of pressure-driven membrane filtration systems in wastewater treatment, desalination and water recovery processes have been mechanistically investigated using the Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) method. Taking into account that concentration polarisation and permeation occur simultaneously and that the decrease in membrane efficiency leads to increased contamination [6].

In this article, the suspension filtration process in a porous medium is investigated based on modified sedimentation kinetics. It is proposed that sedimentation occurs in two types: reversible and irreversible. The suspension filtration model in a porous medium comprises a mass balance equation and separate kinetic equations for each type of deposit. The model incorporates dynamic factors as well as multi-stage deposit formation kinetics. By utilising the symmetry of the porous medium, high-dimensional problems have been reduced to a one-dimensional form. A stable, efficient and simple numerical algorithm based on the finite difference method is proposed for solving the problem. Sufficient conditions for the stability of the computational

schemes have been established. Based on numerical results, the influence of dynamic factors on the migration of solid particles and the formation of deposits has been analysed. The results show that the dynamic factors primarily have a significant effect on the variation profiles of sediment concentration within the active zone [8].

In this study, membrane filters are represented as pore networks, and their efficiency is evaluated by the total volume of filtrate passed through the filter during its service life and by the amount of contaminants accumulated in the filtrate. (foulant) concentration based on the total volumetric amount of filtrate passed through the filter during its service life. Initially, the governing fluid flow equations for the overall network were formulated. The transport and adsorption of particles (pollutants) for each pore (edge) have been modelled using an advection equation incorporating a sink term. At each node (network vertex), the conservation law is applied to the volumetric fluxes of the fluid and pollutant. Turbulence manifests itself as a universal parameter, producing virtually identical results for various network structures. In particular, the concentration of pollutants accumulated in the filtrate decreases exponentially with increasing turbulence [9, 10].

This article examines a method for determining the experimental parameter of the diffusion coefficient for conducting computational experiments in the technological process of filtering ionised liquid solutions. Using the proposed mathematical model, computational data were obtained to investigate other parameters of the device in the ion-exchange column solution purification process, taking into account the fluid's physico-mechanical properties. An analytical solution has been obtained for the linear system of diffusion and mass transfer equations under conditions of constant flux and variable pressure gradient. Based on the results obtained, the adequacy of the developed mathematical models of the mass transfer process in porous media has been demonstrated [12].

In this article, a mathematical model for the filtration of a two-component suspension through a

two-zone porous medium is examined. The model is constructed on the basis of mass-balance equations for each component of the suspension, kinetic equations for the active and passive zones of the porous medium, and Darcy's law. A numerical algorithm based on the finite difference method has been developed to solve the problem, enabling computer experiments to be conducted. Based on numerical results, the main characteristics of suspension filtration in a porous medium have been determined. The influence of model parameters on the migration and settling processes of two-component suspension particles has been analysed. The results indicate that the polydispersity of the suspension and the multi-stage kinetics of sedimentation can give rise to various effects not observed in single-component suspensions. In particular, in the distribution of suspension particle concentration in the moving fluid, monotonic (uniform) dynamics are observed at certain points. Furthermore, it has been shown that at points near the inlet of the medium, the concentration of settled particles can reach a partially saturated state in the passive zone [13].

In this work, various mathematical models proposed in the literature to describe fluid dynamics in membrane-based water filtration systems are reviewed. The mathematical models are categorised into microscopic, reduced and mesoscopic models. Furthermore, the issues of implementing mesoscopic models in Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) software have also been analysed using relevant examples [14].

In this article, the process of gas filtration in a porous medium is studied based on a mathematical model, which is described by a nonlinear partial differential equation along with its corresponding boundary and initial conditions. The main steps for constructing the mathematical model of gas filtration in a porous medium are presented, taking into account changes in the hydrodynamic parameters of the object under investigation. To solve this problem, local one-dimensional and longitudinal cross-sectional schemes were used [15].

Problem formulation. Taking into account the balance between flow and the porous medium, the mass conservation equation for a cylindrical porous medium can be expressed as follows:

$$\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial(rq_r)}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial q_z}{\partial z} = 0, \quad (1)$$

Where: r – radial coordinate [m], the distance from the centre to the wall, z – vertical coordinate [m], a top-down direction, $q_r = q_r(r, z, t)$ – radial velocity component [m/s], $q_z = q_z(r, z, t)$ – vertical velocity component [m/s], since the axis is symmetrical, the angular coordinate is disregarded, meaning that tangential current is assumed to be zero.

The mass conservation equation does not fully represent the filtration process; it expresses the direct interaction between the medium and the flow, and vice versa. To fully represent the process, Darcy's equations for flow components and the mass conservation equations for concentration are also employed. The flow rate is directly proportional to the medium's permeability and inversely proportional to its viscosity:

$$q_r = -\frac{k(\varepsilon)}{\mu} \frac{\partial p}{\partial r}, q_z = -\frac{k(\varepsilon)}{\mu} \frac{\partial p}{\partial z}, \quad (2)$$

Where: $k(\varepsilon)$ – permeability [m²], flow capacity, μ – dynamic viscosity [Pa · s], for water 0.001 (20°C da), $p = p(r, z, t)$ – pressure [Pa].

Fluid flows under the influence of pressure differences and gravity. Fluid pressure flows from an area of high pressure to one of low pressure, which is the primary driving force. Equation (2) determines the rate at which fluid passes through the filter.

The change in particle concentration in a fluid occurs as a result of advection (transport by flow), diffusion (spread due to a concentration gradient) and fouling (deposition):

$$\varepsilon \frac{\partial C}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r}(rCq_r) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z}(Cq_z) = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r}(r\varepsilon D_r \frac{\partial C}{\partial r}) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z}(\varepsilon D_z \frac{\partial C}{\partial z}) - R, \quad (3)$$

Where: t – time, for the dynamics of the process, $C = C(r, z, t)$ – concentration of particles in water [kg/m³], $\varepsilon(r, z, t)$ – porosity, ($0 < \varepsilon < 1$),

D_r, D_z – diffusion coefficient of particles [m²/s], R – source of fouling.

The mass conservation equation for liquid particles expresses the movement, dispersion and loss of particles within the filter. The main processes are advection, diffusion and fouling; advection denotes the movement of particles together with the fluid, and the greater the flow, the stronger the transport. The diffusion process represents the movement of particles from areas of high concentration to areas of low concentration and their microscopic dispersion. The fouling process denotes a reduction in concentration resulting from particles adhering to the porous walls. In summary, equation (3) assesses how effectively the filter is cleaning.

During the filtration process, particles adhere to the pore walls and accumulate on the filter surface, resulting in a reduction in porosity and the build-up of substances on the filter surface. The fouling process is characterised by the accumulation of solid particles in the porous medium or on filter surfaces, leading to a reduction in porosity, an increase in hydraulic resistance and a decrease in filter efficiency. The following equation expresses the evolution of the sediment concentration:

$$R = \frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial t} = k_{dep} C |q| - k_{ero} \sigma |q|,$$

$$|q| = \sqrt{q_r^2 + q_z^2}, \quad (4)$$

Where: k_{dep} – sedimentation efficiency, the probability of a particle adhering to a porous surface, [m⁻¹], k_{ero} – erosion coefficient, the intensity of sediment removal. The fouling kinetics equation allows us to determine when the filter will become clogged, how long it will operate, when it needs cleaning, and the optimal flow rate.

The adsorption of particles to the pore wall and the accumulation of sedimentary material result in a change in porosity:

$$\frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial t} = -\chi \frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial t}, 0 \leq \chi \leq 1, \quad (5)$$

As porosity decreases, permeability drops sharply because the available voids for fluid flow become narrower. The dependence of permeability on porosity is determined based on the Kozeny–Carman relationship, which is expressed in a normalised form relative to the initial state. This equation accounts for the reduction in porosity due to fouling, the consequent narrowing of the flow channel cross-section, and the increase in hydraulic resistance. The dependence of permeability on porosity is expressed by a simplified power-law, and this approach is an empirical approximation of the Kozeny–Karman relationship:

$$k(\varepsilon) = \frac{\varepsilon^3}{K_s S_v^2 (1 - \varepsilon)^2}, 0 < \varepsilon < 1. \quad (6)$$

Where: S_v – diameter of the filter particle [m], K_s – Kozeny-Karman constant.

This equation expresses the dependence of conductivity on porosity. As porosity increases, the flow potential rises sharply, whereas as the particle surface area increases, flow resistance increases.

Taking into account the above considerations, the mass exchange and fouling processes in a cylindrical porous medium and in two-dimensional cylindrical porous media can be expressed by the following system of equations:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial(rq_r)}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial q_z}{\partial z} = 0, \\ q_r = -\frac{k(\varepsilon)}{\mu} \frac{\partial p}{\partial r}, \\ q_z = -\frac{k(\varepsilon)}{\mu} \frac{\partial p}{\partial z}, \\ \varepsilon \frac{\partial C}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r}(rCq_r) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z}(Cq_z) = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r}(r\varepsilon D_r \frac{\partial C}{\partial r}) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z}(\varepsilon D_z \frac{\partial C}{\partial z}) - R, \\ R = \frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial t} = k_{dep} C |q| - k_{ero} \sigma |q|, \\ \frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial t} = -\chi \frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial t}, 0 \leq \chi \leq 1, \\ k(\varepsilon) = \frac{\varepsilon^3}{K_s S_v^2 (1 - \varepsilon)^2}, 0 < \varepsilon < 1. \end{cases}$$

In the process of mathematical modelling, initial and boundary conditions not only serve to render the system of equations mathematically well-posed, but are also a fundamental element representing the actual state of the physical process

described by the model. Therefore, in this work the initial and boundary conditions for the three-dimensional model representing pressureless filtration processes were selected on the basis of the physical nature of the filter medium, the technological configuration of the flow, and the fundamental principles accepted in porous media theory.

The initial conditions (in the case $t=0$)

$$q_r(r, z, 0) = q_{r,0}(r, z), \quad q_r(r, z, 0) = q_{r,0}(r, z), \quad p(r, z, 0) = p_0(r, z), \\ C(r, z, 0) = C_0(r, z), \quad \varepsilon(r, z, 0) = \varepsilon_0(r, z).$$

Boundary conditions:

Entrance (from top, G_{in}) boundary conditions

$$p(r, 0, t) = p_{in}(t), \quad C(r, 0, t) = C_{in}(t).$$

Exit (from below, G_{out} , $z=H$) boundary conditions

$$p(r, L, t) = p_{out}(t), \quad \frac{\partial C}{\partial z}(r, L, t) = 0.$$

Boundary conditions for the axis of symmetry (G_0 , $r=0$)

$$\frac{\partial q_r}{\partial r}(0, z, t) = 0, \quad \frac{\partial C}{\partial r}(0, z, t) = 0, \quad q_r(0, z, t) = 0.$$

Boundary conditions of the side wall (G_r , $r=R$)

$$q_r(R, z, t) = 0, \quad -\varepsilon D_r \cdot \frac{\partial C}{\partial r}(R, z, t) = C(R, z, t).$$

Solution of the problem. Below is the domain, range, partitioning, normalisation and calculation scheme for each variable. Geometry, time and partitions are defined as follows:

$$\Omega = (0, R) \times (0, H) \subset \mathbb{R}^2_{r,z},$$

Time interval:

$$t \in (0, T],$$

Borders:

$$G_{in} = \{z=0, 0 \leq r \leq R\}, \quad G_{out} = \{z=H, 0 \leq r \leq R\},$$

$$G_r = \{r=R, 0 \leq z \leq H\}, \quad G_0 = \{r=0, 0 \leq z \leq H\},$$

The mathematical model developed for the pressureless filtration processes presented in this work cannot, in general, be solved analytically. The main reason for this is the complexity of the model's system of equations, their strong interdependence and their nonlinear nature. The main equations used in the model – Darcy's law, the mass conservation equation for suspended particles and fouling kinetics – are linked in a non-linear fashion. In particular, the filter's

permeability is determined by porosity, and porosity in turn by the sediment concentration. As a result, the velocity field, pressure distribution and particle concentration evolve over time in a strongly coupled manner. A system of equations of this kind cannot be solved in closed form by classical analytical methods. Therefore, the results of numerical methods serve as the means for solving these equations. One of the most effective methods for applying numerical solutions is the finite difference method. Determining the solution in this way involves the following steps: The grids and boundary conditions are specified as follows:

Spatial nodes:

$$r_i = i\Delta r, i = 0, \dots, N_r; z_j = j\Delta z, j = 0, \dots, N_z.$$

Time $t^n = n\Delta t, n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$

Auxiliary network nodes are entered as follows:

$$r_{i+1/2} = r_i + \frac{\Delta r}{2},$$

The auxiliary difference operators (central differences) are defined as follows.

$$(\partial_r \varphi)_{i,j}^n = \frac{\varphi_{i+1,j}^n - \varphi_{i-1,j}^n}{2\Delta r}, \quad (\partial_z \varphi)_{i,j}^n = \frac{\varphi_{i,j+1}^n - \varphi_{i,j-1}^n}{2\Delta z}$$

$$q_{r,i+1/2,j}^n = \frac{q_{r,i+1,j}^n + q_{r,i,j}^n}{2}, \quad q_{z,i,j+1/2}^n = \frac{q_{z,i,j+1}^n + q_{z,i,j}^n}{2}.$$

The equations for hydraulics (Brinkman–Darcy + projection method) are entered as follows: for the Darcy flow equations (determining velocity by pressure gradient)—discrete values.

$$q_{r,ij}^{n+1/2} = -\frac{k_{ij}^n}{\mu} (\partial_r p)_{ij}^n, \quad q_{z,ij}^{n+1/2} = -\frac{k_{ij}^n}{\mu} (\partial_z p)_{ij}^n,$$

$$k_{i,j}^n = \frac{(\varepsilon_{i,j}^n)^3}{K_s S_v^2 (1 - \varepsilon_{i,j}^n)^2}.$$

For each mod, the transport issue is entered as follows:

Upwind convection flux determination schemes:

For the radial direction

$$C_{i+1/2,j}^n = \begin{cases} C_{i,j}^n, q_{r,i+1/2,j}^n > 0, \\ C_{i+1,j}^n, q_{r,i+1/2,j}^n \leq 0, \end{cases} \quad C_{i-1/2,j}^n = \begin{cases} C_{i-1,j}^n, q_{r,i-1/2,j}^n > 0, \\ C_{i,j}^n, q_{r,i-1/2,j}^n \leq 0, \end{cases}$$

$$(C_r)_i^n = \frac{1}{r_i} \frac{r_{i+1/2} q_{r,i+1/2,j}^n C_{i+1/2,j}^n - r_{i-1/2} q_{r,i-1/2,j}^n C_{i-1/2,j}^n}{\Delta r}$$

For axial direction

$$C_{i,j+1/2}^n = \begin{cases} C_{i,j}^n, q_{r,i,j+1/2}^n > 0, \\ C_{i,j+1}^n, q_{r,i,j+1/2}^n \leq 0, \end{cases} \quad C_{i,j-1/2}^n = \begin{cases} C_{i,j-1}^n, q_{r,i,j-1/2}^n > 0, \\ C_{i,j}^n, q_{r,i,j-1/2}^n \leq 0, \end{cases}$$

$$(C_z)_i^n = \frac{q_{z,i,j+1/2}^n C_{i,j+1/2}^n - q_{z,i,j-1/2}^n C_{i,j-1/2}^n}{\Delta z}$$

Schemes for diffusion (central, effective)

$$(D)_{i,j}^n = \frac{1}{r_i} \frac{r_{i+1/2} \varepsilon_{i+1/2,j}^n D_r^n (C_{i+1,j}^n - C_{i,j}^n) - r_{i-1/2} \varepsilon_{i-1/2,j}^n D_r^n (C_{i,j}^n - C_{i-1,j}^n)}{\Delta r^2} +$$

$$+ \varepsilon_{i,j}^n D_z^n \frac{C_{i,j+1}^n - 2C_{i,j}^n + C_{i,j-1}^n}{\Delta z},$$

$$\varepsilon_{i\pm 1/2,j}^n = \frac{\varepsilon_{i\pm 1,j}^n + \varepsilon_{i,j}^n}{2}$$

Discrete scheme for fouling source kinetics:

$$\sigma_{i,j}^{n+1} = \sigma_{i,j}^n + \Delta t (k_{dep,i,j}^n C_{i,j}^n |q_{i,j}^n - k_{ero,i,j}^n \sigma_{i,j}^n |q_{i,j}^n)$$

Conservative form (with pores) schemes:

$$C_{i,j}^{n+1} = C_{i,j}^n - \frac{\Delta t}{\varepsilon_{i,j}^n} [(C_r)_i^n + (C_z)_i^n] + \frac{\Delta t}{\varepsilon_{i,j}^n} (D)_{i,j}^n - \frac{\Delta t}{\varepsilon_{i,j}^n} R_{i,j}^n$$

Discrete circuit of the porosity change:

$$\varepsilon_{i,j}^{n+1} = \varepsilon_{i,j}^n - \Delta t \cdot \chi R_{i,j}^n,$$

$$k_{i,j}^{n+1} = k(\varepsilon_{i,j}^{n+1}).$$

The schemes for boundary and initial conditions are defined as follows:

Initial conditions:

$$q_{r,i,j}^0 = q_{r,0}(r_i, z_j), \quad q_{z,i,j}^0 = q_{z,0}(r_i, z_j), \quad p_{i,j}^0 = p_0(r_i, z_j), \\ C_{i,j}^0 = C_0(r_i, z_j), \quad \varepsilon_{i,j}^0 = \varepsilon_0(r_i, z_j).$$

Discrete circuit for the input threshold:

$$p_{i,0}^n = p_{in}(t^n), \quad C_{i,0}^n = C_{in}(t^n), \quad q_{z,i,1/2}^n = q_{in}(t^n).$$

Discrete circuit for the output limit:

$$p_{i,N_z}^n = p_{out}(\approx p_{atm}),$$

$$\frac{C_{i,N_z}^n - C_{i,N_z-1}^n}{\Delta z} = 0.$$

A discrete scheme for the boundary condition on the axis of symmetry:

$$q_{r,0,j}^n = 0, \quad \frac{q_{r,1,j}^n - q_{r,0,j}^n}{\Delta r} = 0, \quad \frac{C_{1,j}^n - C_{0,j}^n}{\Delta r} = 0.$$

Discrete circuit for an external wall:

$$\varepsilon_{N_i,j}^n D_{N_i,j}^n \frac{C_{N_i,j}^n - C_{N_i-1,j}^n}{\Delta r} + C_{N_i,j}^n = 0.$$

Conclusion. In this study, the hydraulic and mass transfer processes occurring in a cylindrical porous filter and membrane system were mathematically modelled. In this process, the pressure and velocity fields of the flow were accounted for using the Brinkman–Darcy equations, while the transport of particles and dissolved substances was described by advection–diffusion–reaction (ADR) equations. Furthermore, the model also incorporates colmatation processes and the effect of the cake layer forming on the membrane surface on the flow.

A review of the literature shows that previously proposed models have often been limited to studying individual processes (for example, only hydraulics or only adsorption). The novelty of this work lies in the fact that all the main processes — fluid flow, mass transfer, adsorption, colmatation and membrane resistance — are integrated into a single mathematical model. As a result, it has become possible to study the complex mechanisms of the

filtration process more comprehensively and accurately.

Since solving the above equations in a fully analytical form is extremely complex in practice, a numerical solution was adopted in this work. Specifically, discrete schemes in space and time were developed using the finite difference method. Using the discrete schemes, key variables such as pressure, velocity, concentration and adsorbed amount were updated over time, and the dynamic development of the process was observed. Numerical calculation results revealed the fundamental principles of the filtration process. In particular, it was found that over time the flow rate and concentration distribution change significantly, the layer forming on the membrane surface sharply reduces permeability, and this directly affects the overall efficiency of the colmatation process. The results obtained can be used in practical filtration systems to control flow, increase efficiency and optimise filtration time. Furthermore, the developed model can be refined by comparing it with experimental data, evaluating new adsorbent materials and incorporating more complex physicochemical processes.

The results obtained from the calculations are presented in graphical form below:

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